

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP8 – Scientific Coordination, Project Management & Sustainability

D8.20 Report on lessons learned from the conduct of the PoC feasibility assessments and implications for the sustainability plan

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Abstract

The goal of the IMI ConcePTION project is to build an ecosystem for better monitoring and communicating safety of medicines use in pregnancy and breastfeeding. An important element in this ecosystem is the scientific study network. This study network aims to act as a single point of contact for any organisation that wants to conduct a study on medicines in pregnant or breastfeeding persons. The network should give access to a variety of data sources from different countries as well as registering different types of data.

To be able to launch the ecosystem after the conclusion of the IMI ConcePTION project, it is important to gather as much experience with the envisioned model during the lifespan of the project. For this purpose, the consortium has initiated two feasibility studies in order to ‘test’ the study network and to act as a learning device.

In light of the successful implementation of the first two studies with Data Access Providers (DAPs) and the need for continued improvement, the following recommendations and next steps have been identified to optimize the management process of study requests and DAPs:

- Identify incentives for DAPs and Data Requestors.
- Develop a framework agreement with DAPs.
- Develop a quality control framework for DAP Onboarding.
- Identify a Standing Committee and study fit-assessment criteria.
- Develop of a sustainable financial model for post-IMI funding phase.
- Implement a legal frameworks for post-IMI phase.
- Capture learning from conducted studies.

The recommendations form important input for the sustainability discussions in the IMI ConcePTION project during the coming period.

Table of contents

<i>Introduction</i>	3
The aim of the feasibility studies	4
<i>Feasibility assessment study process</i>	6
<i>Feasibility assessments conducted</i>	8
Preliminary learnings: Structure	9
Preliminary learnings: Study implementation	9
<i>Recommendations and next steps</i>	10
Identify Incentives for DAPs and Data Requestors	10
Develop a Framework Agreement with DAPs	10
Develop a Quality Control Framework for DAP Onboarding	10
Identify a Standing Committee and Fit-Assessment Criteria	10
Develop a Sustainable Financial Model for Post-IMI Funding Phase	11
Implement Legal Frameworks for Post-IMI Phase	11
Capture Learnings from Conducted Studies	11
<i>Conclusion</i>	12
<i>Annex 1 – Conclusions from interviews</i>	13
Success factors for DAP engagement in the Study Network	13
The Study Network insurances	13
Business model consideration	14

Introduction

The goal of the IMI ConcePTION project is to build an ecosystem for better monitoring and communicating safety of medicines use in pregnancy and breastfeeding. An important element in this ecosystem is the scientific study network. This study network aims to act as a single point of contact for any organization that wants to conduct a study on medicines in pregnant or breastfeeding persons. The network should give access to a variety of data sources from different countries as well as registering different types of data. A conceptual overview of the ecosystem, and the different elements it contains, is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Overview of the ConcePTION ecosystem

For the scientific study network to be a success, it must fulfil several criteria:

- Operate as a single point of contact to conduct medicine safety studies in pregnant and lactating women.
- Provide the infrastructure to conduct federated analyses in European data sets on medicines use during pregnancy.
- Engage top-level subject experts in projects.
- Provide high-quality results and bring together best-in-class expertise for specific research questions.
- Timesaving for study requestors by being able to conduct their study in a smooth, hassle-free manner.

The study network must be able to answer a variety of questions, for example:

- Information about disease prevalence and outcomes in pregnant and breastfeeding persons.
- Information about medicines utilization in pregnant and breastfeeding persons.
- Information about (treatment) outcomes related to medicines use in pregnant and breastfeeding persons.

The aim of the feasibility studies

To ensure the successful launch of the ecosystem following the completion of the IMI ConcePTION project, it's crucial to accumulate extensive experience with the proposed model throughout the project's duration. To achieve this, the consortium has embarked on two feasibility studies. These studies are designed to evaluate the study network's effectiveness and serve as a tool for learning and improvement.

We requested partners from the IMI ConcePTION consortium to provide us with real-world study requests

that could be conducted as part of the project.

To assess the feasibility of these requests, a secretariat was formed by the WP8 Project Management Office (PMO) team. The secretariat:

- Acts as an intermediary between study requestors and data access providers & research groups;
- Identifies key issues to set up and implement a legal, financial, and governance structure to support the abovementioned activities after the IMI-funding phase.

All activities described below are conducted under the umbrella of the IMI ConcePTION Grant Agreement and the IMI ConcePTION consortium agreement. In this way, we could make use of the existing legal infrastructure for the conduct of these feasibility studies. We understand that any future activities that take place beyond the lifespan of the IMI ConcePTION consortium should have a dedicated legal infrastructure in place. This is described in the section under Recommendations and Next steps.

Feasibility assessment study process

A process was designed for the feasibility assessment, which is described in Figure 2:

Figure 2 – steps in the feasibility assessment

The first step in the process was receiving a **Feasibility assessment request**. This could be from any organization interested in conducting a study through the ConcePTION ecosystem. Requests were submitted using a standardized form shown in Figure 3.

This form requests information about the type of study that is being proposed, the main research question, the type of data sources needed to fulfil the request, the types of outcomes that would need to be studied as well as the expected timeline. The project management team would meet with the study requestor in order to fully understand the study proposed as well as to identify any gaps in the information provided.

Request to conduct feasibility assessment in the ConcePTION ecosystem

Please fill out the details in this form and submit it to Pieter Stolk (P.Stolk@umcutrecht.nl) at the UMCU PMO.

Name of the requestor:

Contact person:

Background of feasibility assessment request:

Aim of feasibility assessment request:

Description of request (What questions need to be addressed by the feasibility assessment):

For example:

- Type of data source
- Counts (i.e. outcomes and confounders)

Expected timeline:

Any other information:

Figure 3 – Form to request Feasibility assessment study.

When the request form was completed, the proposal was discussed in the Sustainability Task Force which would conduct a **Fit assessment**. Where needed, the Secretariat would collect further information about the request or go back to the study requestor in order to have a fully developed dossier that would allow the Sustainability Task Force to make a final decision.

As part of the fit assessment a survey was sent out to all Data Access Providers (DAPs) in the ConcePTION network. The survey that is sent out to the DAPs is shown in Figure 4.

Dectova: Feasibility Assessment Request

Background:
Dectova, zanamivir 10 mg/mL solution for infusion was approved by EMA in April 2019 for the treatment of complicated influenza. Given the increased risk of severe disease in pregnant women, and therefore potential for exposure to Dectova during pregnancy, the requester has a commitment to conduct a post marketing study to assess the safety of exposure to Dectova in pregnant women with complicated influenza and their offspring.

Aim:
The objective of the request is to assess the ability of the ConcePTION data sources to identify pregnant women hospitalized with influenza and their in-hospital/inpatient prescribed medication exposures to determine the feasibility of future studies of Dectova use in pregnant women. This will occur in a phased stepwise approach.

DAPs that are willing to participate in this, please complete all the 3 sections of the questionnaire.

Participating in the Feasibility Assessment

Please answer these questions related to participating in the feasibility assessments.

Section 1
...

General Questions

1. Name of the responder *

2. Email address(es) of the responder

3. Organisation

7. Would your organisation be willing to participate in this feasibility assessment?

8. Would you be able to access data for this feasibility assessment prior to the end of July 2021?

9. If not, what would the rough timeline for accessing the above data be?

10. Is the data source held in your organisation or do you need to receive permission from other organizations to access the data?

All within organisation
 All data reside outside my organisation but it can be accessed
 Some are within my organisation and some outside, but can be accessed and linked
 Other

11. Do you need governance approvals for such assessment?

If yes, please describe any necessary ethics and/or institutional approvals that your organisation would need to obtain to participate, including timelines:

Figure 4 – survey sent out to DAPs.

The survey requests detailed information from each DAP and also requests them to indicate whether they can execute the study and in which timeframe. This information was provided to the Sustainability Task Force to support decision-making.

During this phase of the project, the criteria for the fit assessment were not formalized; the fit assessment was mainly done based on the experience and expertise of Sustainability Task Force members. Going forward, it is of importance to define specific criteria for the Fit Assessment in order to provide transparency and predictability for decision making (see Recommendations and Next Steps).

If a study request was deemed to be of sufficient quality, as well as feasible within the context of the ConcePTION ecosystem, the next step would be taken: the **Selection of a Feasibility Coordinator**. Based on the information provided and our knowledge about the partners in the consortium, one organization was selected to coordinate the scientific part of the study. This organization was responsible for drafting the study plan, collating and analyzing results and writing the final report.

The writing of the study plan/7rotocoll was done In the **Feasibility Outline Proposal** phase. Once the protocol was finished and aligned with the study requestor and the MT, the actual study would take place: the **Carry out feasibility assessment** phase. The final step of this phase was the provision of a report with the results from the DAPs to the study requestor.

Feasibility assessments conducted

During the project, we have received five requests for the conduct of a feasibility study. Of these, two made it to the execution stage. One study focused on the occurrence of Multiple Sclerosis in pregnant women, and one study focused on Dectova, an antiviral medicine. For both studies, the work of the consortium was supported by a Direct Financial Contribution (DFC) from the requesting partners. A short description of the two case studies can be found in Box 1 and Box 2.

Multiple sclerosis case study objective

Sanofi has regulatory requirements regarding their multiple sclerosis (MS) drugs and vaccines to study use of their product and the outcomes of pregnancy during pregnancy until one year after end of pregnancy. Prospective registries have not yielded the required number of exposed pregnancies, and the company is now exploring the use of health care data through the ConcePTION ecosystem.

Study Output

A count of the:

- Number of women 15-55 years of age for 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019.
- Number of a) with prevalent or existing MS diagnosis in each calendar year: 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019.
- Number of b) getting pregnant or giving birth (please specific what you do) in each calendar-year: 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019
- Number of c) with exposure to MS drugs (teriflunomide and alemtuzumab) at any time during pregnancy (between LMP and end of pregnancy).

Number of women getting pregnant with use of any of the vaccines of interest:

- Quadrivalent meningococcal conjugate vaccines MenACWY (e.g. brand names: Menveo, Nimenrix).
- Flu vaccines (e.g. brand names: Vaxigrip, Vaxigrip Tetra, Fluad, Influvac Tetra).

Box 1 - Multiple Sclerosis case study

Dectova case study objective

The objective is to identify pregnant women hospitalized with influenza and their in- hospital/inpatient prescribed medication exposures to determine the feasibility of future studies of Dectova use in pregnant women. These involve the following sub-questions:

1. The number of women of childbearing potential (WOCBP) with influenza hospitalized during the last 5 flu seasons years pre-COVID, i.e. 2014/15, 2015/16, 2016/17, 2017/18, 2018/19?
2. The number of pregnant women with influenza were hospitalized during the last 5 flu seasons years pre-COVID, i.e. 2014/15, 2015/16, 2016/17, 2017/18, 2018/19?
3. For the data sources/DAPs with the potential to capture in-hospital infusions what are the proportion of mothers successfully linked to babies?

Optional: Among women (WOCBP and pregnant) hospitalized with flu, how many were admitted to ICU?

Study Output

Following data analysis, i.e., estimation of pregnant women with influenza hospitalized by the DAPs, the results or “counts” will be presented in an appropriate table form.

Box 2 - Short description of the Dectova case study

During the execution of the Feasibility Studies we encountered several challenges, implemented mitigation strategies and formulated recommendations based on this.

Preliminary learnings: Structure

Challenge	Mitigation measures applied	Future solutions
Contracts needed with each of the third-party DAPs	DAPs started to work while contracting was underway	Develop a framework with DAPs
Delay in approval of cash grant letters provided by requestors	Asked UMCU legal team to “fast track” the review	Develop a standard template?
Standing committee members not yet identified		Could involve key MB members during the project phase
Fit assessment criteria not yet identified		Develop it based on advice provided by standing committee

Preliminary learnings: Study implementation

Challenge	Mitigation measures applied	Future solutions
Ethical permissions	Use counts from other related studies (GSK Dectova)	Develop a (legal) framework that allows for quicker approvals
Lukewarm response from some DAPs for study request	Individually contacted DAPs and explained process	An onboarding document or webpage for new DAPs with clear descriptions and FAQs
Quality control of the protocols or scripts used by the DAPs	None, so far	Quality-check committee/team

Recommendations and next steps

Considering the successful implementation of the first two studies with Data Access Providers (DAPs) and the need for continued improvement, the following recommendations and next steps have been identified to optimize the management process of study requests and DAPs. These measures aim to streamline administrative procedures, foster collaboration, and ensure the efficient functioning of the ConcePTION Ecosystem with regard to studies using secondary data.

These recommendations need to be translated into an action plan which will need to provide clear milestones and go/no go decisions. For the ecosystem to be able to launch successfully after the project closure, these recommendations at least 6 months before the end of the project.

Identify Incentives for DAPs and Data Requestors

To foster active engagement and sustained commitment from DAPs and data requestors, suitable incentives (financial, scientific, governance) should be introduced. These may include financial incentives, recognition programs, or preferential access to research findings. This is the subject has been the focus of a series of interviews separate from this task, which the consortium will discuss at the MB meeting on the 14th of November. Such financial incentives need to be detailed upfront, moreover there need to be clearcut agreements about what is expected from DAPS (e.g. in terms of response time), please also see the remarks about the framework agreement below. Additionally, fostering a collaborative environment that promotes knowledge-sharing and networking will encourage ongoing participation and strengthen the DAP community, this is the job of the secretariat of a future ConcePTION consortium ecosystem. Sufficient investment needs to be available to maintain and grow the ecosystem. Potentially, this could be run from staff seconded by project partners. An extensive discussion of how DAPs can best be integrated into the study network was part of the work of WP7. A summary of the key conclusions related to DAPs is included as Annex 1.

Develop a Framework Agreement with DAPs

To expedite the contracting process and reduce administrative burdens, a comprehensive framework contract with DAPs should be developed. If a detailed contracting process is required for each individual study, this would lead to unneeded delays. This framework should incorporate standardized terms and conditions, while allowing flexibility to accommodate study-specific requirements. Topics that should be discussed in an agreement include IP, access rights to results, liabilities, dispute resolution, timelines, financial conditions, decision procedures among others. By streamlining the contracting process, we can facilitate swift project initiation and minimize delays in data access.

Develop a Quality Control Framework for DAP Onboarding

To maintain a high standard of performance among all DAPs, a robust quality control framework, along the lines of current international standards for data quality, for their onboarding must be established. This framework will encompass stringent criteria for evaluating potential DAPs, emphasizing their track record, data access capabilities, and commitment to the program's objectives. By rigorously screening DAP applicants, we can ensure that only the most qualified and reliable entities are granted participation, thereby elevating the overall quality of data access and research conducted within the program.

Identify a Standing Committee and Fit-Assessment Criteria

To facilitate effective decision-making and oversight, the establishment of a dedicated Standing Committee is recommended. This committee should comprise representatives from data providers, data requestors, regulatory bodies, and data privacy experts. Their collective expertise will foster diverse perspectives in evaluating proposed data access projects and prioritizing them based on societal needs and research potential. Key components of fit-assessment for a study proposal are: feasible objectives and goals, solid methodology, a clear data analysis approach, and a robust quality control mechanism, among others. As part of the discussions around sustainability a suitable governance structure will need to be developed (e.g.

as part of an international association or foundation).

Develop a Sustainable Financial Model for Post-IMI Funding Phase

To guarantee the program's long-term viability, a financial model for the post-IMI funding phase must be devised. This is currently being discussed as part of the sustainability work stream and will be the subject of Management Board decision making in November 2023. This model should consider diversified funding sources, including public and private contributions, corporate sponsorships, and grants. Additionally, a clear outline of how the DAP secretariat will be funded should be established, ensuring consistent operational support.

Implement Legal Frameworks for Post-IMI Phase

As the DAP initiative evolves, it is prudent to explore potential legal frameworks for the post-IMI (Innovative Medicines Initiative) phase. This entails examining the most suitable legal structure to continue DAP operations beyond the current project timeline. Legal experts should be consulted to ensure compliance with data protection regulations and facilitate smooth transitions. The IHI Grant and Consortium Agreement provide a basis for determining how results should be treated after the end of the project. For specific results that are included in an ecosystem, specific arrangements will need to be made that address issues such as ownership and data protection.

Capture learnings from conducted studies

To cultivate a culture of continuous improvement, it is essential to gather insights and experiences from the future studies. This includes obtaining feedback from all stakeholders, including participating data providers, data requestors, and beneficiaries. By analyzing the feedback, we can identify pain points, bottlenecks, and success factors. This information will inform an updated process flow that maximizes efficiency and addresses any identified issues, ensuring seamless operations in future DAP studies.

Conclusion

The conduct of the Proof-of-Concept (PoC) feasibility assessments within the ConcePTION project has provided insights into the strengths and limitations of the current scientific study network model. These early studies have not only demonstrated the technical viability of conducting federated analyses across multiple Data Access Providers (DAPs) but have also highlighted key operational, legal, and governance challenges that must be addressed to ensure the long-term sustainability of the ecosystem.

The experiences gained underscore the importance of developing standardized processes, clear incentives, robust governance mechanisms, and a sustainable financial and legal framework. The recommendations outlined, ranging from the establishment of a Standing Committee and fit-assessment criteria to the development of quality control systems and legal agreements, are essential for transitioning the study network into a functional and independent post-IMI phase.

As the project concludes, these lessons learned will need to be translated into actionable steps with defined milestones. Doing so will enable the ConcePTION ecosystem to mature into a scalable, trusted, and efficient platform for studying medicine safety in pregnancy and breastfeeding, ultimately contributing to improved maternal and child health outcomes across Europe and beyond.

Annex 1 – Conclusions from interviews

This Annex summarizes some of the important success factors that have surfaced through interviews undertaken with DAPs by Marieke Hollestelle, as part of WP7, and some principles about how the study network could be governed and run to maximize the engagement and contribution of DAPs to the network.

Success factors for DAP engagement in the Study Network

- Each DAP is autonomous at all times about whether to remain part of the network or not, what categories of data they are willing to make available for network originating studies, and whether to participate in each proposed study.
- Each DAP must provide precise and accurate information to populate their entry in the data catalogue and have a regular process for maintaining their catalogue entry.
- Some DAPs may nominate one or more senior investigators who wish to be invited to contribute to study design teams, in which they may participate on an *ad hoc* basis, to help develop the appropriate data study methodology or to contribute to a feasibility analysis.
- DAPs may nominate one or more senior investigators who wish to be involved in the analysis of data, derived across the network, that will lead to the definitive research findings from one or more studies.
- DAPs will be encouraged to provide data management expertise regarding the data that they hold when feasibility analyses and actual data studies are being performed, in order to ensure the most relevant, fit for purpose, data is extracted and analyzed on each occasion.
- DAPs will support high quality research by undertaking data quality analyses from time to time, at the request of the study network coordinator, sharing back those findings and being willing to undertake data quality and data mapping activities that maximize the reliability and value of its data, taking into account that funding may be required for substantial improvement activities.
- When agreeing to participate in a feasibility analysis or full data study, DAPs must ensure they have capacity to deliver their data and analytics contributions within the proposed timeframe of the study.
- DAPs that themselves operate as data networks will be responsible for negotiating any data access and permissions from their contributing data sources for any data study that they agree to participate in.
- DAPs will be responsible for securing any ethics committee or other permissions required for its participation in a data study.
- DAPs must always be free to withdraw from a data study if they discover issues of which they were not aware in advance that conflict with their own policies and terms of operation.

The Study Network insurances

- The Study network must ensure that DAPs are given sufficient and timely information about each requested feasibility analysis or full data study in order to be able to consider their participation, including transparency about the research sponsor and the source of funds.
- DAPs that have signalled their wish to contribute senior investigator expertise to feasibility analysis, study design or study data analysis are invited to do so for each relevant study.
- The arrangements for data access, financial or in-kind support and recognition with each DAP are formalized in a data access agreement.
- DAPS are appropriately acknowledged as data providers and/or study co-authors, agreeing the terms in advance of active participation.
- It always follows academic good practices in defining, conducting and recognizing contributions to data studies.
- It establishes an open and transparent governance model, operational model and financial model.
- Its governance is appropriately inclusive of DAP representatives, alongside other stakeholders.
- Its infrastructure incomes do not come directly from industry. (Discussion is needed on whether it would be acceptable for its infrastructure funding to come from overheads charged on feasibility and data studies, including some of those that have an industry funding source.)

- Industry sponsored studies must be transparently declared and be both designed and conducted independently from the sponsoring company. In cases where industry co- participation in study design and conduct is considered appropriate, this must be transparently declared before seeing DAP and expert involvement.
- It is open and inclusive across its DAP network when inviting participation in feasibility analyses and data studies.
- It identifies, contracts with and appositely finances a lead organization with responsibility for each data study.
- The necessary portfolio of permissions across its data network are in place before orchestrating or conducting a data study.
- There is adequate documentation and internal transparency about the DAP selection, data selection, processing and analysis steps undertaken during a data study, for traceability and potential downstream justification evidence of the findings.
- It develops and maintains a code of conduct covering its governance and operations, in addition to the adoption of codes of conduct (e.g. ENCePP) for specific data studies.

Business model considerations

- The study network must establish a transparent and regularly reviewed financial model that distributes fee income from feasibility and data studies appropriately between its central operational needs, business development needs, external experts and advisory board costs, and funds it can share with DAPs to compensate for their efforts in providing data and expertise.
- The study network must allocate a portion of its business activity and funding to attracting new data studies and promoting the importance and value of the network.
- The study network must be sensitive to the restrictions on funding sources that may apply to some DAPs, seeking as far as possible to allocate funds to DAPs from acceptable sources.
- The study network must seek as soon as possible to secure sufficient infrastructural incomes that it can offer some funding support to DAPs that need this, a share of that infrastructural funding to support their own infrastructure (staff, equipment etc.).
- The study network must seek as often as possible to offer in kind computational and data analytics support to DAPs that need it.
- The study network must transparently define and regularly review an over-arching scientific scope to the studies it will investigate and conduct.
- The study network must ensure that the sponsor of each data study request is encouraged to make the scientific findings public (i.e. academically published) even if the results are also utilized for product or service development, risk & safety management or regulatory applications.